

Table1:

Lithofacies	Miall Code	Sedimentary features and form	Fossils and artifacts	Interpretation
Palaeosol	P	paedogenic carbonate are present with fine sandy clay (7.5 YR 7/4). Around 3.5m thick and sedimentary structure less deposition. Roots are present	Gastropod shell, microlithic and shell beads and also in the basal part the animal bones fossils are presented.	The depositions are developed with floodplain origin and soil development.
Fine laminated silty-clay	Fl	Massive unit of heterogeneous yellow sand (10YR 6/5) mixed with micas and silt. Calcrete nodules and roots.	shells are presents	Slow sedimentation of the biogenic-rich facies; suspension in a low-energy environment, as indicated by the fine grain size, lack of sorting
Cross-bedded channel sand (Micaceous)	Cs	This lithofacies consists of massive, matrix-supported sheets of pebbly coarse sand, colour mostly yellowish-orange (7.5YR 6/4, 10YR 6/3) in nature, poorly sorted planar cross-bedded medium to fine sand.	Shell fragments and few microlithic artifacts and charcoal presents mostly deposited through floods	It reflected deposition by 1/2 sheet flow event with high-energy pulse represented by pebbly coarse micaceous sand.
Ash layer	YTT	Volcanic clastic fine grey (10YR 7/1) colour material; Massive with sharp undulating upper contact and sharp planar lower contact	Nil	Abandoned channel/pond/ lake sediments on a floodplain
Kankar/calcretes	CaCO ₃	Sub-angular to sub-rounded carbonate nodules (5-10 mm) in the matrix of poorly sorted sand.	Occurs as very thin layers of few cm; carbonate formed in fossils layer also	pedogenic modification of floodplain deposits. Also indication of sub-humid to dry condition
Massive mud	Fm	Grey to blackish clay layer rich in organic matter	Shell fragments are present	lakes filled with sediments are drained and represent low-energy condition; rich in organic matter

Table2:

Sample ID	Depth (m)	U (ppm)	Th (ppm)	K (%)	Dose rate (Gy/ka)	De (Gy)	Age (ka)
BK3	3.6	2.50±0.13	6.40±0.3	1.70±0.1	2.58±0.14	45.19±1.5	17.52±1.1

Table3:

Sample No	χ_{lf}	χ_{fd}	χ_{fd} %	χ_{ARM}	SIRM	HIRM	S-Ratio %	L ratio	$B_{(O)CR}$
BKA-1	0.71	0.01	1.25	6.44	36.34	2.78	34.29	0.48	60
BKA-2	0.62	0.01	1.33	5.57	27.2	2.41	32.65	0.35	130
BKA-3	0.51	0.02	1.57	5.18	17.07	1.15	37.45	0.36	80
BKA-4	0.45	0	0	5.73	15.95	1.03	39.23	0.35	74
BKA-5	0.41	0.01	0.68	5.63	15.55	0.92	38.67	0.35	77
BKA-6	0.41	0.01	1.22	4.52	11.88	0.66	41.69	0.33	72
BKA-7	0.43	0.02	1.71	4.7	15.37	0.84	41.24	0.31	75
BKA-8	0.53	0.02	1.65	5.48	17.25	0.89	41.32	0.33	66
BKA-9	0.39	0.01	0.87	4.77	17.99	1.31	36.85	0.38	80
Minimum	0.39	0	0	4.52	11.88	0.66	32.65	0.31	60
Maximum	0.71	0.02	1.71	6.44	36.34	2.78	41.69	0.48	130
Mean	0.49	0.01	1.14	5.34	19.4	1.33	38.15	0.36	79.33
SD	0.11	0.01	0.55	0.61	7.58	0.75	3.18	0.05	20.08

Table4:

Localities	River Valley/Country	Reference	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	MnO	CaO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	Total
Pawlaghat	Narmada river basin, India	Shane et al. (1995)	77.15	0.06	12.65	0.86	0.08	0.06	0.78	3.26	5.07	99.9
Goguparhu	Vansadhara river basin, India	Westgate et al. (1998)	77.67	0.07	12.14	0.89	0.06	0.05	0.75	3.24	4.98	99.8
Morgaon	Karha river basin, India	Gatti et al. (2014)	77.26	0.05	12.34	0.89	0.05	0.07	0.79	3.31	5.24	100
Bori	Kukadi River	Gatti et al. (2014)	77.73	0.05	12.21	0.88	0.06	0.06	0.81	3.28	5.21	100
Jwalapuram	Jurreru river	Gatti et al. (2014)	77.73	0.05	12.28	0.88	0.08	0.05	0.72	3.37	5.12	100
Kapileshwar (primary)	Purna river	Srivastava and Singh (2019)	76.6	0.06	12.2	0.9	0.05	0.06	0.8	2.7	4.3	98.6
Kapileshwar (Secondary)	Purna river	Srivastava and Singh (2019)	68.05	0.16	14.67	3.57	0.23	0.21	1.87	3.26	5.01	104
Bori	Kukadi River	Shane et al (1995)	77	0.05	12.6	0.89 (FeO)	0.06	0.07	0.76	3.35	5.04	99.8
Guruwara	Narmada river basin, India	Acharyya and Basu (1993)	68.18	0.67	15.9	5.01	0.57	0.09	5.58	1.82	2.28	100
Tejpur	Madhumati River	Raj (2008)	71.15	0.48	13.23	3.47	1.4	0.09	1.54	2.53	3.52	97.4
Toba Tuff Sumatra (Sample 70)	Sumatra	Chesner (1998)	70.36	0.46	15	3.32	0.74	0.08	2.8	3.45	3.61	99.8
Bengal Fan	Bay of Bengal	Gasparotto et al. (2000)	77.2		12.85	0.85	0.07		0.72	3.2	5.11	100
Toba Caldera	Sumatra	Chesner and Luhr (2010)	76.88	0.09	12.56	0.91	0.09	0.07	0.95	3.21	5.23	99.9
Lake Malawi	East Africa	Lane et al. (2013)	77.24	0.05	12.41	0.84	0.07	0.05	0.77	2.95	5.61	99.9
Barakar (Pre-treatment)	Barakar River	Present study	76.23	0.05	12.18	0.91	0.06	0.06	0.76	3.32	5.22	98.79
Barakar (Bulk)	Barakar River	Present study	67.15	0.11	15.62	3.46	0.58	0.11	1.67	3.36	5.11	97.17

